

THE NEED FOR DEVELOPING CANVA-BASED INTERACTIVE LEARNING MEDIA TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' LITERACY ABILITIES

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Abstract

This research aimed to analyze the need for developing Canva-based learning media to improve the literacy skills of Phase B students at Public Elementary School. The problems faced in the field are students' lack of literacy skills to understand and reason, students are not enthusiastic when asked to read, after reading students cannot understand the content that they have read so they are unable to retell the content of the reading, and students appear less interested when asked. to read using a reading textbook. These problems underlie this development need analysis research. This research used a non-associative quantitative analysis research methodology. The research sample consisted of 52 people from 110 populations. The results of this development need analysis research recommend that it is necessary to develop Canva-based interactive learning media to improve students' literacy skills.

Keywords: development needs, interactive learning media, Canva, literacy skills

INTRODUCTION

Literacy is related to the ability to read, write, speak, and process information obtained and solve problems in everyday life (Oktariani & Ekadiansyah, 2020; Ananda & Rakhmawati, 2022; Hidayati et al., 2024). Literacy is an important ability that must be possessed by every individual, including students because it can help students in the learning process. Literacy is not only reading and writing but also includes critical thinking skills by utilizing printed, visual, and digital sources of knowledge (Rohim & Rahmawati, 2020; Wahyuni et al., 2024). Literacy skills are very important in the 21st century (Nugroho & Dewi, 2024; Lupo et al., 2024).

Students are expected to be able to construct meaning from a text into various forms. Two factors can influence students' literacy skills, namely internal factors that come

from within the student and factors external that come from outside the student (Khasanah et al., 2024). The low literacy skills in Indonesia are of course an important problem in the world of education (Ulfa et al., 2023). This can be seen from the students' ability to complete Minimum Competency Assessment (AKM) questions which is still low. The Minimum Competency Assessment (AKM) is part of the national assessment to measure basic competencies in the form of literacy and numeracy (Megawati & Sutarto, 2021; Andriani et al., 2024).

Technological advances have had a significant impact on the world of education (Ruswan et al., 2024; Novianto & Nadawina, 2022; Lesmana et al., 2019). Of course, it can also be used to improve students' literacy skills. A teacher must have a reason why a learning model is chosen and guarantee that the learning model implemented is effective in supporting the

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success of educators in getting students to understand a problem through all stages of the learning process carried out following the stated objectives (Lesmana & Arpan, 2017; Dewi, 2018; Sii et al., 2017; Simanungkalit & Tarigan, 2022; Arpan et al., 2022).

Teachers can use advances in information technology to increase creativity in creating learning environments. Teacher creativity is very necessary, especially in the use of learning media (Abidin, 2019; Budiman et al., 2018). But in reality, information technology has not been utilized optimally. Learning media has a very important role in the learning process. With the creativity possessed by a teacher, learning media can be developed into something interesting and motivate students to be more active in learning (Sulistiyarini et al., 2018; Liwayanti, 2021; Sanulita et al., 2024).

So that learning becomes more meaningful. Learning media can make it easier to interact between teachers and students and help the learning process to be more optimal (Triningsih, 2021; Feladi et al., 2017). Learning media can be a key focus for the integration of technology in the field of education. From an educational perspective, instructional media is a strategic instrument that can support the success of the teaching and learning process (Arsyad, 2011; Arpan & Budiman, 2018; Fajri & Sahlan, 2023; Arianto et al., 2023).

Based on psychological studies, students find it easier to learn concrete things compared to abstract ones. Learning media can provide concrete experiences and serve as a mediator to assist students in their learning (Wulandari et al., 2023; Kusnasari & Rakhmawati, 2022). Therefore, it is crucial to choose the right media that can capture the attention of learners (Ramadhani & Anshari, 2022; Syaifullah et al., 2024). Technology based learning media has numerous benefits for education, including capturing students' interest and improving their learning outcomes (Firmadani, 2020; Hernando et al., 2022; Budiman et al., 2022; Miharja,

2022; Riance et al., 2024; Sopanda et al., 2022).

The term "media" is derived from the Latin word "medius" which translates to "middle, intermediary, or mediator". Learning media serves as an instructional tool that can be employed in the learning process to channel the thoughts and abilities of learners (Kholifa & Pujiharti, 2021). Learning media can be utilized to convey instructional information from educators to learners. The expectation is that the use of learning media will enhance learners' motivation in the learning process.

To achieve effectiveness in the use of learning media, innovation in the development of instructional media is necessary. One approach is through the development of interactive learning media. Interactive learning media is a combination of two or more elements such as audio, text, graphics, images, animations, or videos (Wahyuni et al., 2020; Astriyani, 2022). This undoubtedly requires creativity during planning, production, and utilization.

Interactive learning media leverages computer technology or other electronic devices to present educational content to learners (Ramadhani et al., 2023). Interactive learning media can be tailored to the learners' progress, utilizing the advancements in ever-evolving technology. Consequently, it can create a more personalized learning experience for each student. Proper utilization can enhance the unique abilities of learners, enabling meaningful learning outcomes (Tuwoso et al., 2021).

Canva is an interesting learning media and can be designed by teachers themselves according to their learning needs (Ardana et al., 2022). The Canva application has various features that are in line with current developments. Using the Canva application in learning can attract students' attention (Putri & Mudinillah, 2021). It is hoped that Canva's learning media can facilitate students to improve their literacy skills. The use of Canva learning media can influence student learning outcomes (Citradevi, 2023; Darwis et al., 2024).

METHOD

This research used a non-associative quantitative analysis research methodology. The research sample was phase B students at SD Negeri 13 Muaro, totaling 52 people from a population of 110. The sampling technique employed used proportional random sampling, which is a method used to obtain samples by drawing them randomly in proportion to the size of each sampling unit, which is the smallest part used to determine the sample size.

The data collection technique was carried out using a questionnaire with yes and no answer options. There are 4 indicators with a total of 15 questions answered by the sample. These indicators were: (1) students' literacy skills with 4 questions; (2) students' reading interest with 3 questions; (3) the role of parents with 3 questions; (4) the use of technology with 5 questions. This research was carried out at SD Negeri 13 Muaro. The percentage of scores obtained was grouped into very high, high, medium, low, and very low criteria with a scale as in the following Table 1.

Table 1. Rating Scale

Scale	Category
90-100	Very High
80-89	High
65-79	Medium
55-64	Low
0-54	Very Low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted to analyze the need for developing interactive learning media to improve students' literacy skills. This arose in connection with the researcher's concerns about the situation in the field involving the research team as teachers in elementary schools. Based on the results of the questionnaire that was filled out by students, the following results were obtained.

Results

Inferential analysis is conducted to test the research hypotheses. The obtained data should have a normal distribution. Normality testing aims to determine whether the development needs analysis questionnaire used in the study originates from a population with a normal distribution. Here are the results of the normality test for development needs using

SPSS 20.0 for Windows software.

Table 2. The Results of Normality Test

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
The need for developing	.119	52	.061	.979	52	.474

Based on Table 2, using SPSS 20.0 for Windows software on the Test of Normality employing the Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test with the criteria $Sig. > \alpha$, with a significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Consequently, the Sig. value obtained is $0.061 > \alpha = 0.05$. It can be interpreted that the data originates from a normal distribution.

Student Literacy Ability

For student's literacy abilities, researchers asked 4 questions. The following are questions used as indicators of student literacy abilities. This can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Indicator of Student Literacy Ability

Question	Question Number
I can read fluently	1
I can write fluently	2
I can understand the text that is read	3
I can retell the text I read	4

The following are the results obtained for the literacy ability indicators for phase B students at Muaro 13 Public Elementary School.

Table 4. Student Literacy Abilities

Category	Number of Students	Percentage
Very High	10	19.23%
High	5	9.62%
Medium	18	34.61%
Low	19	36.54%
Very Low	0	00.00%
Total	52	100.00%

Based on Table 4, the group of students in the very high category, there were 10 students (19.23% of the total sample). For the group of students in the high category, there were 5 students (9.62% of the total sample). For the group of students in the medium category, there were 18 students (34.61% of the total sample). For the group of students in the low category, there were 19 students (36.54% of the total sample). And for the group of students in the very low category there are 0 students (00.00% of the total sample).

Figure 1. Percentage for Each Literacy Ability Evaluation Indicator Question

Based on Figure 1, the average student's reading ability was 93% in the very high category. The student's writing ability was 82% in the high category. The ability to understand reading content was 65% in the medium category. The ability to retell reading content was 64% in the low category. The average percentage for the student Literacy Ability indicator was 76% in the medium category.

Student's Reading Interest

For indicators of reading interest, researchers asked 3 questions. Here were the questions used to indicate students' reading interests.

Table 5. Indicator of Reading Interest

Question	Question Number
I like to read	5
I always make time to read	6
I am interested in reading books	7

The following are the results obtained for the reading interest indicators for phase B students at Muaro 13 Public Elementary School.

Table 6. Student's Reading Interest

Category	Number of Students	Percentage
Very High	12	23.08%
High	10	19.23%
Medium	4	7.69%
Low	0	00.00%
Very Low	26	50.00%
Total	52	100.00%

Based on Table 6, the group of students in the very high category, there were 12 students (23.08% of the total sample). For the group of students in the high category, there

were 10 students (19.23% of the total sample). For the group of students in the medium category, there are 4 students (7.69% of the total sample). For the group of students in the low category there are 0 students (00.00% of the total sample). And for the group of students in the very low category, there are 26 students (50.00% of the total sample).

Figure 2. Percentage for Each Question Indicator of Student Reading Interest

Based on Figure 2, the results showed that the average number of students who like reading was 74% in the medium category. Students who took the time to read showed an average of 62% in the low category. The interest in reading books shows an average of 72%. So, the average result obtained for the student reading interest indicator was 69% in the medium category.

The Role of Parents

For indicators of parental role, 3 questions were given. This can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Indicators of Parental Role

Question	Question Number
My parents like to read	8
My parents have a collection of reading books	9
My parents always invite me to read together	10

The results obtained for indicators of the role of parents in phase B students at Muaro 13 Public Elementary School are as follows.

Table 8. Role of Parents

Category	Number of Students	Percentage
Very High	4	7.69%
High	10	19.23%
Medium	14	26.93%
Low	0	00.00%
Very Low	24	46.15%
Total	52	100.00%

Based on Table 8, the categories for

indicator parental role based on results tabulation data. For the group of students in the very high category, there were 4 students (7.69% of the total sample). For the group of students in the high category, there were 10 students (19.23% of the total sample). For the group of students in the medium category, there were 14 students (26.93% of the total sample). For the group of students in the low category there are 0 students (00.00% of the total sample). For the group of students in the very low category, there were 24 students (46.15% of the total sample).

Figure 3. Percentage for Each Parental Role Indicator Question

Based on Figure 3, the result showed that the average of parents who like to read was 71% with a medium category. The elderly has a collection of reading books was 61% with a low category. The parents invite students to read at home was 63% with a low category. The average result for the indicator of the role of parents was 65% with a moderate category.

Utilization of Technology

For indicators of technology utilization, 5 questions are given. The questions used are as follows at Table 9. The following are the results obtained for indicators of technology use for phase B students at Muaro 13 Public Elementary School at Table 10.

According to Table 10, the group of students in the very high category, there were 46 students (88.47% of the total sample). For the group of students in the high category, there was 1 student (1.92% of the total sample). For the group of students in the medium category, there were 4 students (7.69% of the total

sample). For the group of students in the low category, there were 0 students (00.00% of the total sample). For the group of students in the very low category, there was 1 student (1.92% of the total sample).

Table 9. Indicators of Technology Utilization

Question	Question Number
I have gadget	11
I have read using gadget	12
I was interested when reading about using gadget	13
I'm more interested in reading using gadgets compared to books	14
I can understand the contents of the reading after reading using a gadget	15

Table 10. Technology Utilization

Category	Number of Students	Percentage
Very High	46	88.47%
High	1	1.92%
Medium	4	7.69%
Low	0	00.00%
Very Low	1	1.92%
Total	52	100.00%

Figure 4. Percentage for Each Question of Technology Utilization Indicators

Based on Figure 4, the average student who has a gadget was 99% in the very high category. Students who have read use gadgets was 99% in the very high category. For students who are interested in reading using gadgets was 95% in the high category. Students who are more interested in reading use gadgets compared to books was 93% in the very high category. To understand the content of the reading after

reading using a gadget was 88% in the high category. The average tabulation result for the technology utilization indicator was 95% in the very high category.

Results of Analysis of Literacy Ability Indicators

Based on the results of the analysis according to tabulated data on literacy ability indicators, students' reading ability was very good. Students' ability to write was also good. However, the ability to understand the content of the reading and the ability to retell the content of the reading that has been read still needs to be improved.

Results of Analysis of Students' Reading Interest Indicators

Based on the results of the analysis according to tabulated data on indicators of student reading interest, students who like to read and their interest in reading still need to be improved. Meanwhile, taking time to read still requires special attention because there are still many students who don't do it.

Results of Analysis of Parental Role Indicators

Based on the results of the analysis according to data tabulation on indicators of the role of parents, the results showed that parents' interest in reading needs to be increased. Special attention is needed for parents' reading book collections and the role of parents in inviting students to read together at home must be greatly enhanced.

Results of Analysis of Technology Utilization Indicators

Based on the results of the analysis according to data tabulation on technology utilization indicators, results were obtained. Almost all students have gadgets, never read using gadgets, are interested while reading using gadgets, and feel more interested in reading when using gadgets compared to books. Many students are able to understand the content after using gadget.

Discussion

The following is a presentation of indicator data for analysis of development

needs to improve the literacy skills of phase B students at Muaro 13 Public Elementary School.

Figure 5. Indicators of Development Needs to Improve Literacy Skills

Based on Figure 5, it can be seen that the use of technology can be used to improve students' literacy skills because 95% of students were more interested in using technology in literacy activities. Students need interactive learning media that can improve literacy skills. One interactive learning media that can be used is Canva-based interactive learning media. Canva provides various interesting designs and features.

Referring to research that has been conducted previously, the research results based on t-test obtained count 9.187 higher than t-table 2.000. The average value of initial reading ability in the experimental group was greater than the control group, namely 87.27 compared to 65.77. It can be stated that students who use Canva-based interactive multimedia have better initial reading abilities compared to students who do not use Canva-based interactive multimedia (Aulia et al., 2023). This means that using Canva-based multimedia has a significant impact.

Furthermore, the other research results found that the impact of using the Canva application as a learning medium in 21st century learning is that students become more active, creative, confident, and can equip students with the 4C skills students need to answer the challenges of the 21st century (Hidayatullah et al., 2023). This development needs analysis research is expected to have a positive impact on improving students' literacy skills by making the most of the IT facilities available at the school.

CONCLUSION

Based on the conducted research, it can be concluded that the analysis of development needs

for Canva-based interactive learning media to enhance student literacy skills suggests the necessity for the development of interactive learning media based on Canva in the learning process to improve students' literacy skills. The development of Canva-based interactive media is expected to facilitate students in understanding learning materials and enhance the literacy skills of students. According to the findings of the conducted needs analysis research, it is expected that the development of interactive learning media based on the Canva application can be carried out and utilized in the learning process.

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